

Theoretical and methodological bases public management and administration

Serhii Maistro, Vitalii Kropyvnytskyi, Nelli Leonenko

National University of Civil Defence of Ukraine

Abstract. The differences between the scientific definitions of “governance”, “public management” and “public administration” are defined. The author's definition of the concept of “public management and administration” is given. A methodological approach to assessing the effectiveness of public management and administration is proposed.

Implementation of the long-term sustainable development strategy of Ukraine requires a corresponding transformation of the public administration system, which, among other things, is conditioned by the emergence and active use in the educational and scientific sphere of such concepts as “public management” and “public administration”.

Thus, on September 1, 2015, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine “On Approving the List of Fields of Knowledge and Specialties Under which Higher Education Applicants Are Trained” entered into force in Ukraine, pursuant to which a new branch of knowledge 28 “Public management and Administration” was introduced, and new specialty 281 “Public management and administration” [1].

Therefore, the formation and implementation of an effective system of public management and administration in modern conditions requires a clear theoretical and methodological definition of the main conceptual categories and its differences from the concept of “governance”.

In a narrow sense, public administration is seen as a professional activity of civil servants, which includes all activities aimed at implementing government decisions, as an interdisciplinary academic field based on the theory and concepts of economics, political science, sociology, administrative law, management. In a broad sense, public administration is understood as the whole system of administrative institutions with a hierarchy of power, through which the responsibility for the implementation of state decisions goes from top to bottom [2].

According to the encyclopedia of public government, public administration is a kind of management of public authorities, through which the state and civil society ensure the self-management of the entire social system and its development in a certain, specific direction [3].

Ponkin I. considers that, in general, the concept of "public administration" reflects an integrated systemic mechanism, subsystems and elements of which are political program guidelines and priorities, regulations, procedures funded by the state or local governments, centralized, and decentralized organizational and management structures and their staff, responsible for the administration of activities in a particular area of public relations at the supranational, subnational and local levels [4].

According to a global study “Governance Matters”, governance is understood as the totality of traditions and institutional formations by which public authorities govern a country [5].

20 November 2020

In general, the concept of "public governance" reflects an integrated systemic mechanism, subsystems and elements of which are political policy orientations and priorities, normative regulation, procedures financed by the state or local self-government bodies, centralized and decentralized organizational and management structures, and their respective entities for the administration of activities in a particular field of public relations at the national, subnational and local levels [6].

Filipova N. notes that public governance studies the interaction between the political system, the public sector, the relationship of municipal, state and national interests in involving society in the mechanism of control of all authorities [7].

The term "public governance" was first used by English public servant D. Keeling, who believes that public administration is the search for the best way to use resources to achieve priority public policy goals [8].

Consider the definition of "public administration", because very often this concept is identified with government and does not differentiate its essence.

Administration is in itself a management activity, since the Latin word *administratio* means "service", "help", "management". Administration is the prerogative of executive authorities or officials (civil servants) [9].

Kiliyevich O. clarifies the essence of the concept of public administration in the "English-Ukrainian Glossary of Terms and Concepts in the Analysis of State Policy and Economy", revealing its structure:

first, the public sector covers institutions both national and regional, and also the Institute of Local Self-Government;

secondly, the concept of public policy as a compromise between state and public is better translated as public policy, that is, policy pursued in society and for society;

third, "public administration" should be understood as public governance or the implementation of public policy by a predominantly executive branch [10].

The term "public administration" in the glossary of the United Nations Development Program has two closely related meanings:

1) holistic state apparatus (policies, rules, procedures, systems, organizational structures, personnel, etc.) financed by the state budget and responsible for managing and coordinating the work of the executive branch of power and its interaction with other stakeholders in the state, society and the external environment;

2) management and implementation of various governmental measures related to the implementation of laws, regulations and decisions of the government and management related to the provision of public services [11].

According to Pffiner J. and Presthus R., "public administration is the management of the organization and direction of human and material resources to achieve the desired goals" [12].

Martynenko V. believes that public administration is a form of public administration implemented by representative bodies of democratic governance through their executive structures [13].

According to Lazor O., public management and administration are management activities that have both common and distinct characteristics. The main difference is that public administration is implemented by public figures, making political decisions, administration – the activities of professional managers (officials, public servants) – aimed at preparing and implementing these decisions, as well as overseeing their implementation [14].

In the narrow sense, public administration is seen as a professional activity of civil servants, which includes all activities aimed at implementing government decisions, as an interdisciplinary academic field, based on the theory and concepts of economics, political science, sociology, administrative law, management. In a broad sense, public administration

20 November 2020

is understood to mean the whole system of administrative institutions with a hierarchy of power, through which responsibility for the implementation of state decisions goes down from above [15].

According to the encyclopedia of public administration, public administration is a kind of management activity of public authorities, whereby the state and civil society ensure the self-management of the entire social system and its development in a certain, defined direction [16].

Also under-explored is the question of the relation between the concepts of "governance", "public management" and "public administration".

Minenko M. notes that in the public sector, the "bureaucratic model" has become a "market model" - the emphasis has shifted from performing work in accordance with instructions and clear rules to work aimed at providing quality public services and achieving effective results, which, in its turn, led to the transformation of "governance" into "public management" and eventually into "public administration" [17].

According to Filipova N., governance is a component of public management, and the essence of public administration combines the other two and contributes to the accomplishment of the tasks set by the authorities [18].

Therefore, the concepts of "governance", "public management", "public administration" are not identical and synonymous.

In our view, public governance and administration are purposeful, systematic, consistent and public activities of public authorities and local self-government bodies in the public interest through the activities of administrative institutions through appropriate mechanisms of influence to create conditions for competitive sustainable development of the country and increase the level of well-being society.

Determining Ukraine's place in the world economy, it should be understood that it largely depends on the effectiveness of public management and administration. Therefore, it is important to choose the right criteria for assessing the effectiveness of public management and administration in the context of globalization, which will depend on the further sustainable development of the country.

In our view, current approaches to determining the effectiveness of public management and administration should include a set of indicators that characterize the nature and effectiveness of public policy in all its spheres. Therefore, we attach the utmost importance to the principle of systematicity, and we believe that the effectiveness of public administration and administration should be based on a system of indicators.

Governance Matters (Quality of public administration) is a global study and its accompanying ranking of countries around the world in terms of quality and effectiveness of public governance. The research methodology uses six indexes (Worldwide Governance Indicators), reflecting various parameters of public administration [19]:

1. Voice and Accountability;
2. Political Stability and Absence of Violence;
3. Government Effectiveness;
4. Regulatory Quality;
5. Rule of Law;
6. Control of Corruption.

Therefore, modern public management and administration should contribute to the long-term sustainable development of the country, taking into account the economic, social and environmental components. To this end, it is necessary to make full use of the possibilities of increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of the system of public management and administration by: taking into account the opinion of the population and accountability of public authorities; the achievement of political stability and the absence of violence; increase of efficiency of work of state authorities and local self-government;

20 November 2020

improving the quality of legislation; ensuring the rule of law; curbing corruption in all its manifestations.

So, public management and administration - at the same time the management of the government, which is tied to the structure, the adoption and implementation of administrative decisions in the intergovernmental bodies and enterprises, the establishment of the context of the government. Ukraine's transition to European standards of public relations, the development of a democratic state governed by the rule of law require an effective, flexible, adapted to the new challenges of the system of public management and administration. After all, improving the efficiency and quality of the national system of public management and administration is one of the main conditions for ensuring sustainable socio-economic development of the country as a whole, as well as a major factor in improving the welfare of citizens.

References

1. On approving the list of branches of knowledge and specialties for which higher education applicants are trained [Pro zatverdzhennya pereliku haluzey znan' i spetsial'nostey, za yakymy zdiysnyuyet'sya pidhotovka zdobuvachiv vyshchoyi osvity]: Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of April 29, 2015. – No. 266. Web. 24 Mar. 2020, <<http://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/266-2015-%D0%BF>>.
2. Kupryashin, G. State management: opportunities and limitations [Gosudarstvennyy menedzhment: vozmozhnosti i ogranicheniya]. Public administration. Electronic newsletter. – 2003. – № 1. Web. 20 Mar. 2020, <<http://www.spa.msu.ru>>.
3. Bahrah, D., Rossinsky, B., Starilov, Y. Administrative law [Administrativnoye pravo]. – M.: Norma, 2008. – 816 p. Print.
4. Ponkin, I. General theory of public administration: Selected lectures. [Obshchaya teoriya publichnogo upravleniya: Izbrannyye lektsii]. International Institute of Public Administration and Management of the Academy of National Economy and Public Administration. – M., 2013. – 196 p. Print.
5. The quality of government [Kachestvo gosudarstvennogo upravleniya]. Web. 20 Mar. 2020, <<https://gtmarket.ru/ratings/governance-matters/governance-matters-info>>.
6. Surmin, Y. Public Administration. [Publichne administruvannya]. Encyclopedic Dictionary of Public Administration. – K.: NADU, 2010. – 605 p. Print.
7. Filipova, N. Changing the relation between the concepts of "governance", "public governance", "public administration" in the system of socio-political transformation. Public Administration: Improvement and Development. – 2015. – № 6. Web. 21 Mar. 2020, <http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Duur_2015_6_5>.
8. Keeling, D. Management in Government / D. Keeling (1972), London: Allen&Unwin. Print.
9. Obolensky, O. The basic synopsis of lectures in the discipline. [Oporny konspekt lektsiy z navchal'noyi dystsypliny]. Public Administration: Scientific Development. – K.: NADU, 2011. – 56 p. Print.
10. Kilievich, O. The Anglo-Ukrainian Glossary of Terms and Concepts in the Analysis of State Policy and Economy [Anhlo-ukrayins'kyy hlosariy terminiv i ponyat' z analizu derzhavnoyi polityky ta ekonomiky]. – K.: Fundamentals, 2003. – 510 p. Print.
11. Chernov, S. Public Administration and Administration in the Information Society: Domestic and Foreign Experience [Publichne upravlinnya ta administruvannya v umovakh

20 November 2020

informatsiynoho suspil'stva: vitchyznyanyy i zarubizhnyy dosvid]: monograph. – Zaporizhia: ZDIA, 2016. – 606 p. Print.

12. Pfifner, J., Presthus, R. Public Administration. – New York: The Ronald Press Co., 1960. – P. 3. Print.

13. Martynenko, V. Democratic governance: problems of theory and practice [Demokratychnе vryaduvannya: problemy teorii ta praktyky]. Public Administration: Theory and Practice. – Kh., 2010. – № 1. – P. 16-22. Print.

14. Lazor, O. Public administration and administration: a retrospective of some theoretical aspects [Publichne upravlinnya ta administruvannya: retrospektyva deyakykh teoretychnykh aspektiv]. University Scientific Notes, 2015, No. 56, pp. 111-121. Print.

15. Public Administration Review. – Vol. 56. – N 3 (May – Jun., 1996). – P. 247-255. Print.

16. Encyclopedia of Public Administration [Entsyklopediya derzhavnoho upravlinnya]. At 8 vols. – Vol. 8: Public Governance. – Lviv: LRIDU NADU, 2011. – 712 p. Print.

17. Minenko, M. Transformation of the system of public administration into modern models of regulation of society [Transformatsiya systemy derzhavnoho upravlinnya v suchasni modeli rehulyuvannya suspil'stva.]. Public Administration: Improvement and Development. Web. 22 Mar. 2020, <<http://www.dy.nayka.com.ua/?op=1&z=581>>.

18. Filipova, N. Changing the relation between the concepts of "governance", "public governance", "public administration" in the system of socio-political transformation. Public Administration: Improvement and Development. – 2015. – № 6. Web. 21 Mar. 2020, <http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Duur_2015_6_5>.

19. The quality of government [Kachestvo gosudarstvennogo upravleniya]. Web. 20 Mar. 2019, <<https://gtmarket.ru/ratings/governance-matters/governance-matters-info>>.